

Full Length Article

Nanoparticle doping and molten-core methods towards highly thulium-doped silica fibers for 0.79 μm -pumped 2 μm fiber lasers – A fluorescence lifetime study

Petr Vařák^{a,b,*}, Martin Leich^c, Michal Kamrádek^a, Jan Aubrecht^a, Ondřej Podrazký^a, Ivo Bartoň^a, Bára Švejkarová^a, Alena Michalcová^d, Katrin Wondraczek^c, Matthias Jaeger^c, Ivan Kašík^a, Pavel Peterka^a, Pavel Honzátko^a

^a Institute of Photonics and Electronics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Chaberská 1014/57, 182 51, Prague, Czech Republic

^b Department of Inorganic Chemistry, University of Chemistry & Technology, Prague, Technická 5, 162 00, Prague, Czech Republic

^c Leibniz Institute of Photonic Technology, Albert-Einstein-Str. 9, Jena, 07745, Germany

^d Department of Metals and Corrosion Engineering, University of Chemistry & Technology, Prague, Technická 5, 162 00, Prague, Czech Republic

A B S T R A C T

We study the fluorescence lifetime of Thulium-doped silica fibers for efficient laser operation in the 2 μm “eye-safe” wavelength range pumped by 0.79 μm radiation. A large set of optical fibers prepared by Modified Chemical Vapor Deposition combined with solution doping or nanoparticle doping, and Molten-core method is investigated in terms of fluorescence lifetimes of the $^3\text{F}_4$ and $^3\text{H}_4$ excited levels, which contain information about the Tm^{3+} ion environment, the rate of unwanted processes, such as concentration quenching or multiphonon relaxation, as well as the inter-ionic energy-transfer processes, including the cross-relaxation. Maximum evaluated lifetime values are 778 μs for the $^3\text{F}_4$ level and 56 μs for the $^3\text{H}_4$ level. From the lifetime study, we conclude that for Tm^{3+} concentrations above 10,000 ppm and enhanced aluminum concentrations above 5 mol. % Al_2O_3 , the cross-relaxation efficiency is enhanced and multiphonon relaxation is remarkably reduced due to the lower phonon energy of the resulting aluminosilicate glass.

1. Introduction

Rare-earth (RE) doped fiber lasers represent one of the major scientific breakthroughs of the 20th century, owing to various advantages over the gas or crystal based counterparts, such as excellent beam quality, feasible thermal management and cooling, as well as flexibility and practicality of use [1]. In particular, thulium-doped fiber lasers (TDFL) and amplifiers (TDFA), based on the trivalent Tm^{3+} ions, represent an attractive option for emission in the “eye-safe” range around 2 μm , since the light in this region is absorbed mainly by the vitreous parts of the eye, minimizing the damage to retina [2–4]. The 2 μm emission originates from the $^3\text{F}_4 \rightarrow ^3\text{H}_6$ transition between energy states of the 4f electrons, as depicted in Fig. 1. The TDFL and TDFA devices are interesting thanks to the possibility of pumping by 0.79 μm radiation into the $^3\text{H}_4$ level, using commercially available diodes. In theory, the Stokes limit for the 2 μm emission using 0.79 μm excitation would limit the maximum achievable efficiency to around 40 %. However, a significant advantage of the Tm^{3+} ion lies in the cross relaxation process $^3\text{H}_4, ^3\text{H}_6 \rightarrow ^3\text{F}_4, ^3\text{F}_4$, also called the “2-for-1” process, depicted in

Fig. 1, in which an ion in the $^3\text{H}_4$ excited state transfers part of its energy to a neighboring ion in the ground state, $^3\text{H}_6$, resulting in both ions populating the laser-active $^3\text{F}_4$ level. The CR process essentially allows to populate the $^3\text{F}_4$ energy level with two excited ions at the cost of one absorbed photon into the $^3\text{H}_4$ level, allowing 200 % quantum efficiency and therefore up to 80 % energy conversion efficiency, two times the Stokes limit [5–7].

The design of TDFL devices using the 2-for-1 process places a significant requirement on the material. The effective 2-for-1 process requires a high concentration of Tm^{3+} ions since the CR process is inversely proportional to inter-ionic distance, d , by a factor of $1/d^6$ – the lower the distance between the Tm^{3+} ions, the higher the probability of the energy transfer [8]. The CR effect typically occurs when the concentration of Tm^{3+} ions is higher than 4,000 ppm (approx. 1.2 wt. % of Tm_2O_3), but concentrations above 10,000 ppm (approx. 2.5 wt. % of Tm_2O_3) are generally required to truly take advantage of this effect and achieve efficiencies above 60 % [2,5]. Silica glass, the most commonly used material in fiber-optic technology, exhibits a very low solubility of RE ions, which results in the formation of clusters even at low

* Corresponding author. Institute of Photonics and Electronics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Chaberská 1014/57, 182 51, Prague, Czech Republic.

E-mail address: varak@ufe.cz (P. Vařák).

Fig. 1. Diagram of energy levels of Tm³⁺ ions, showing the ground state and the three lowest excited states relevant for the operation of 2.0 μm-emitting lasers; red lines = absorption, blue lines = radiative emission, grey lines = non-radiative multiphonon relaxation, green lines = cross-relaxation (CR), purple lines = energy-transfer upconversion (ETU), brown lines = pair-induced quenching (PIQ).

concentrations below 100 ppm, leading to concentration quenching, where deleterious processes, such as pair-induced quenching (PIQ) or energy transfer up-conversion (ETU), are preferred over the desired 2-for-1 process [9,10]. Moreover, the high phonon energy of the silica network leads to high rates of multiphonon relaxation, where the energy is dissipated into the matrix as heat in the form of vibrational phonons [11,12]. These effects combined lead to a rapid, non-radiative depopulation of the excited levels, which causes short fluorescence lifetime and sub-standard laser performance [13,14]. Obtaining silica-based materials with high RE concentration while maintaining strong emission and high fluorescence lifetime requires the introduction of other dopants, which prevent the concentration quenching and provide low-phonon energy environment for Tm³⁺ ions, the most notable being Al₂O₃ [15–17].

The most widespread and traditional method for the fabrication of RE-doped silica fibers is the Modified Chemical Vapor Deposition (MCVD) combined with solution doping, where a porous silica layer is deposited on the inner side of a pure silica tube using gaseous SiCl₄, and subsequently soaked with a solution containing AlCl₃ and TmCl₃ [18, 19]. However, this method is limited in the achievable Al₂O₃ concentration around 5 mol. %, which also limits the maximum Tm³⁺ content before the onset of concentration quenching [20]. In general, achieving concentrations higher than 5,000 ppm of RE ions while maintaining sufficient laser performance represents a complex task.

The rapidly advancing development of TDFL and TDFA devices therefore requires new methods for the preparation of highly-doped fibers. In the past decade, various novel methods or modifications to the MCVD were presented, a review can be found in Ref. [21]. To name a few, highly doped fibers up to 8.5 wt. % of Tm³⁺ with laser efficiencies above 70 % were prepared by vapor phase deposition of Al or Tm using chelates or halide vapors [22,23]; improved emission and laser characteristics were also achieved by *in-situ* solution doping, where the solution is poured into the tube directly in the MCVD lathe [24]. The fabrication of highly-doped, highly-efficient fibers by solution doping was recently reported by commercial enterprises, but no further specifics about the fabrication process were disclosed [25].

Amongst the most prospective methods are also the MCVD method combined with nanoparticle doping and the molten-core (MC) method. The nanoparticle doping is a more advanced extension of the classic solution doping, where the chloride-based solution is replaced by nanoparticle dispersion, containing either synthesized RE:Al₂O₃ or RE:AlO(OH) nanoparticles [26,27] or pure Al₂O₃ nanoparticles mixed with RECl₃ [14,28]. The main advantage of the nanoparticle doping lies in

the possibility to introduce higher amounts of Al₂O₃, up to 12 mol. %, which raises the achievable RE content without the onset of concentration quenching. We previously used the nanoparticle doping method for the preparation of Ho³⁺-doped fibers and achieved a slope efficiency of 83.1 %, more than 89 % of theoretical maxima and on par with state-of-the-art literature [14].

The molten-core method is based on a completely different principle, i.e., using solid-state precursors, such as crystals, glasses or semi-conductors [29]. In the case of aluminosilicate fibers, a crystalline rod, typically YAG or sapphire, is inserted into a silica tube and drawn at temperatures, where the core material is fully melted but the cladding only softened [30]. The diffusion between the core and cladding produces a silicate core containing high concentrations of Al₂O₃ up to 40 mol. % [31,32]. The molten-core fibers typically exhibit high background attenuation caused by impurities from the solid state precursors, but the high achievable dopant concentrations show a potential for a strong enhancement of emission properties, as well as reduction of non-linear effects, such as stimulated Brillouin or Raman scattering, which are one of the main obstacles for high power output [33,34].

One of the most useful characteristics for the evaluation of “spectroscopic quality” of the Tm³⁺-doped optical fibers are the fluorescence lifetimes of the ³F₄ and ³H₄ excited levels [35]. The fluorescence lifetime of the ³F₄ level strongly correlates with laser parameters such as slope efficiency and laser threshold – it was consistently shown that fibers with high fluorescence lifetime of the laser-active level exhibit enhanced laser operation [13,36]. Moreover, the ³H₄ level is highly sensitive to the inter-ionic energy transfer processes, such as ETU or CR, and the fluorescence lifetime of the 0.8 μm emission thus provides information about the efficiency of the CR process [37]. Aside from bringing essential information about the material itself, the fluorescence lifetime is a necessary parameter in various theoretical tasks, such as calculation of energy-transfer coefficients [37,38], or simulations of laser and amplifier operation [39], including the effects of temperature [40]. The precise knowledge of the fluorescence lifetime and the compositional dependency is therefore necessary for the efficient design of optical fibers for high-power lasers.

In this paper, we present a thorough study of fluorescence lifetime of optical fibers prepared by MCVD method combined with solution or nanoparticle doping, as well as the molten-core method. The optical fibers were prepared in a wide range of Al₂O₃ and Tm³⁺ concentrations and characterized with respect to the fluorescence lifetime of the ³F₄ and ³H₄ levels. The compositional trends and relationships between the various methods were analyzed, and the advantage of the nanoparticle doping and molten-core methods was discussed. The potential for efficient laser operation was analyzed and discussed.

2. Experimental

2.1. Preparation of samples

Several experimental methods were used in this work for the preparation of optical fibers. At the IPE ACS in Prague, the optical fibers were fabricated by the Modified Chemical Vapor Deposition (MCVD) combined with solution or nanoparticle doping. In the solution doping (SD) process, the porous silica frit was soaked with an ethanolic (99.9 %, VWR) solution of aluminum chloride (AlCl₃ anhydrous, 99.999 %, Sigma-Aldrich) and thulium (III) chloride (TmCl₃·6H₂O, 99.99 %, Sigma-Aldrich). In the nanoparticle doping (NP) process, a doping suspension was used. The suspension consisted of TmCl₃·6H₂O and aluminum oxide nanoparticles of <50 nm size (γ-Al₂O₃, 99.9 %, Sigma-Aldrich) in absolute ethanol. The suspension was freshly sonicated before use in order to minimize the risk of nanoparticles agglomeration. Selected preforms were shaped to octagonal shape using CO₂ laser to achieve a suitable geometry for cladding pumping. We have previously shown that the cladding geometry has no impact on the fluorescence lifetime measurement [10]. Optical fibers were drawn with cladding

diameter in the 120–140 μm range (precision $\pm 1 \mu\text{m}$) and core diameter in 7–20 μm range. The detailed description of the preform fabrication and fiber drawing can be found in Refs. [14,41].

At the Leibniz IPHT in Jena, the optical fibers were prepared by the molten-core method, using a silica cladding tube with inserted Tm-doped YAG rod as core precursor. All preforms were drawn to fibers with similar outer diameter of 130 μm . Detailed description of the fabrication and basic characterization of the prepared fibers can be found in Ref. [42].

2.2. Characterization of samples

Dopant concentrations in the original MCVD preforms were measured by a JEOL JXA 830 electron probe microanalyzer (EPMA). The refractive index profiles of the preforms were measured using a Photon Kinetics A2600 refractive index profiler, and the refractive index profiles of the optical fibers were measured using an IFA-100 refractive index profiler. The background losses were measured using a halogen lamp and ANDO AQ6317 optical spectrum analyzer, and evaluated from absorption spectrum minimum. Selected fiber was analyzed by EDS coupled to TEM, the sample preparation procedure was identical as in Ref. [43]. The sample was observed by EFTEM Jeol 2200FS field emission electron microscope in TEM mode. The elemental composition was analyzed by energy-disperse spectroscopy (EDS) in STEM mode with 1 nm spot size.

The samples were characterized regarding fluorescence lifetime. The detailed description of the measurement setup can be found in Ref. [28]. Fluorescence decay curves were measured using semiconductor diodes emitting at 792 nm (Lumics LU793M250 diode) or 785 nm (QFLD-785-250S) as an excitation source. The emission was detected by InGaAs (Hamamatsu) or Si (Thorlabs PDA series) photodiodes. The measured fibers were approximately 1 mm long, and emission was detected from the side in order to suppress the influence of amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) and reabsorption [13]. The decay curves were measured for multiple excitation powers in the range of 0.1–170 mW; decay times for each respective excitation power were obtained

from the 1/e value of the normalized intensity. The fluorescence lifetime, i.e., the decay time extrapolated to zero pump power, was obtained using Equation (1):

$$\tau = \frac{\tau_0}{1 + \left(\frac{\tau_0}{\tau_{\text{SAT}}} - 1 \right) \cdot \left(\frac{P}{P + P_{\text{CRIT}}} \right)^2} \quad (1)$$

where τ is the decay time obtained from the 1/e intensity on the normalized decay curve, P is the excitation power, τ_0 is the fluorescence lifetime (the decay time extrapolated to zero excitation power), τ_{SAT} is the saturated lifetime (the decay time extrapolated to infinite excitation power), and P_{CRIT} is the critical excitation power. Values of τ_0 , τ_{SAT} and P_{CRIT} were thus obtained as fitted parameters for each respective sample [41].

3. Results

3.1. List of optical fibers and general characteristics

The summary of the studied fibers is presented in Table 1. In total, 24 optical fibers are included in the study. The fibers can be segregated into several groups based on the fabrication method and dopant concentrations. 8 fibers were prepared by the conventional solution doping method and contain concentrations up to 5 mol. % of Al_2O_3 and 10,000 ppm of Tm^{3+} ions. Subsequently, 13 fibers were prepared by the more advanced nanoparticle doping. Of these, 4 optical fibers were in the same concentration range as the solution doped fibers, while 9 fibers contained elevated dopant concentrations up to 12 mol. % Al_2O_3 and 25,000 ppm of Tm^{3+} ions. In addition, 3 fibers were prepared by the molten-core method, with dopant contents up to 25 mol. % of Al_2O_3 and 17,000 ppm of Tm^{3+} ions, basic characterization of the prepared fibers can be found in Ref. [42]. In addition, the molten-core fibers contained a significant amounts of Y_2O_3 , which further serves to decrease concentration quenching and multiphonon relaxation.

The refractive index differences between the core and the cladding of the preforms and final fibers were in a reasonable agreement with the

Table 1

The overview of the general properties of the prepared optical fibers; SD = solution doping, NP = nanoparticle doping, MC = molten core method; *includes Y as the (Al+Y)/Tm ratio. The concentration of Tm^{3+} ions is given in ppm according to convention as outlined in Ref. [44]. Note that the Tm^{3+} ppm are related to Tm_2O_3 mol. % by a factor of 20,000 (10,000 ppm Tm^{3+} = 0.5 mol. % Tm_2O_3).

Fiber	Method	Al_2O_3 (mol. %)	Tm^{3+} (ppm)	Al/Tm	$\Delta n_{\text{preform}} \cdot 10^{-3} (-)$	$\Delta n_{\text{fiber}} \cdot 10^{-3} (-)$	Att. (dB/m)	$\tau(^3\text{F}_4)$ (μs)	$\tau(^3\text{H}_4)$ (μs)
<i>$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 < 5$ mol. %</i>									
P1480A	SD	3.0	700	90	6.0	6.0	0.014	495	28.6
P1338B	NP	4.3	1000	88	6.4	5.7	0.310	511	29.4
P1593	NP	3.3	800	88	6.9	7.9	0.077	516	31.2
P1480B	NP	1.8	900	41	4.2	4.6	0.017	447	26.1
P1283	SD	4.2	1,700	49	9.6	9.3	0.019	523	30.4
P1338A	SD	3.4	1,900	36	7.1	7.0	0.017	488	28.1
P1290	SD	4.8	1,400	68	10.8	10.0	0.019	490	29.0
P1481A	SD	2.4	2,500	19	5.6	5.6	0.023	430	24.4
P1587L	SD	2.8	2,700	21	5.9	5.9	0.072	425	24.4
P1481B	NP	2.4	6,500	7	6.3	7.0	0.027	372	20.4
P1363	SD	2.6	7,000	7	8.2	7.2	0.025	398	21.0
P1510	SD	2.2	10,000	4	8.0	8.5	0.089	373	17.3
<i>$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 = 5 - 12$ mol. %</i>									
P1604L	NP	9.8	100	1,960	20.5	18.0	0.044	778	56.0
P1201R	NP	11.9	1,600	144	25.4	23.9	0.350	731	46.0
P1603	NP	7.7	1,700	86	16.3	15.2	0.087	695	36.8
P1618	NP	9.5	5,400	35	25.3	23.7	0.049	643	28.1
P1691	NP	10.8	11,900	18	27.6	26.1	0.125	554	19.7
P1598R	NP	8.1	12,300	13	23.5	24.2	0.013	553	19.3
P1545	NP	8.0	12,800	13	22.3	21.8	0.037	567	20.1
P1607	NP	8.1	15,400	10	24.6	22.7	0.022	519	16.9
P1530	NP	5.6	25,400	4	22.9	22.3	0.101	482	13.2
<i>$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 > 15$ mol. %</i>									
J456	MC	16.5 (+8.8 Y_2O_3)	3,900	131*	–	113.6	2	760	44.5
J458	MC	15.8 (+8.2 Y_2O_3)	10,600	45*	–	104.1	1.9	610	32.0
J481	MC	25.6 (+9.8 Y_2O_3)	16,700	42*	–	117.3	2.4	710	29.3

dopant concentrations; higher dopant content results in higher core-cladding difference. The solution and nanoparticle doped fibers exhibited a generally reasonable background attenuation below 0.1 dB/m in the 850–1000 nm range. A pattern of slightly higher attenuation was generally observed in fibers with high contents of Al_2O_3 or Tm^{3+} , and thus higher refractive index. On the other hand, the molten-core fabricated fibers exhibited higher attenuation values around 2 dB/m. The increased attenuation and scattering present an obstacle, e.g., for laser operation or data transmission, but the fluorescence lifetime measurement and evaluation remain reliable and comparable.

3.2. Measurement of the fluorescence lifetime

The fluorescence lifetimes of the $^3\text{F}_4$ and $^3\text{H}_4$ level were measured in an identical manner for all fibers, two representative fibers are shown here in detail. Fig. 2a and b show the fluorescence decay curves of the 2 μm emission (from the $^3\text{F}_4$ level) and the 0.8 μm emission (from the $^3\text{H}_4$ level) of the P1338B fiber; this fiber was prepared by the nanoparticle doping and contained 4.3 mol. % of Al_2O_3 and 1,000 ppm of Tm^{3+} ions. The fluorescence decay curves exhibit typical behavior with increasing deviations from single-exponentiality at high powers, which leads to faster fluorescence decay [13]. This effect can be ascribed to the depopulation of the $^3\text{F}_4$ and $^3\text{H}_4$ levels by the inter-ionic energy transfer effects, such as ETU or CR, which occur to a certain degree despite the low Tm^{3+} content. The fluorescence lifetime extrapolated to zero power exhibits relatively high values of 511 μs and 29.4 μs for the $^3\text{F}_4$ and $^3\text{H}_4$ levels, resp., which suggests low rates of concentration quenching. The fluorescence lifetime of the $^3\text{H}_4$ level is one order of magnitude lower than the $^3\text{F}_4$ level, since the $^3\text{H}_4$ level in silica suffers from very high rates of multiphonon relaxation due to the close proximity to the lower-lying $^3\text{H}_5$ level, as seen in Fig. 1.

Fig. 2c and d shows the fluorescence decay curves of the P1618 fiber, also prepared by the nanoparticle doping, but containing elevated concentrations of 9.5 mol. % of Al_2O_3 and 5,400 ppm of Tm^{3+} ions. The fluorescence decay of the 2 μm emission exhibits single-exponential behavior at low powers. The decrease of decay time with increasing power is more pronounced compared to the previous fiber, likely due to

the higher Tm^{3+} content and therefore higher rate of ET processes. The extrapolation to zero power gives the fluorescence lifetime for the $^3\text{F}_4$ level of 643 μs , an enhanced value compared to P1338B fiber, despite higher concentration of Tm^{3+} , which can be attributed to the higher content of Al_2O_3 . The decay from the $^3\text{H}_4$ level gives more complex results. The decay curves of the 0.8 μm emission contain a long “tail”, whose contribution to the fluorescence decay curves increases with excitation power, leading to increase of the decay time. This effect can be ascribed to the strong presence of ET processes. The CR process first leads to a fast depopulation of the $^3\text{H}_4$ level, and the increase of population in the $^3\text{F}_4$ level in turn leads to the repopulation of the $^3\text{H}_4$ level by the ETU. Since the lifetime of the $^3\text{F}_4$ level is significantly longer compared to $^3\text{H}_4$ level, a long tail appears in the measured curves and the fluorescence lifetime increases with excitation power. This kind of behavior indicates a potentially efficient CR process, and can be typically observed in fibers with concentrations of at least 5,000 ppm, as shown here, which is in a good agreement with the commonly given threshold for the CR process.

3.3. Fluorescence lifetime of the $^3\text{F}_4$ level (2 μm emission)

The fluorescence lifetime values were measured and evaluated for all fibers listed in Table 1 in the same manner as in Fig. 2. The fluorescence lifetime values of the $^3\text{F}_4$ level are compiled in Fig. 3a as a function of absolute Tm^{3+} concentration. Despite some scattering, clear trends are evident. The fluorescence lifetime of fibers prepared by each method decreases with Tm^{3+} concentration due to the concentration quenching; the $^3\text{F}_4$ level is depopulated by ETU processes as the inter-ionic distance decreases. On the other hand, the fluorescence lifetime increases with Al_2O_3 content. Al_2O_3 added into pure silica acts primarily as network modifier, breaks the rigid silica network and creates structural cavities, which incorporate the Tm^{3+} ions, and thus reduce the clustering and concentration quenching [16,17,45].

The values of fluorescence lifetime plotted as a function of the Al/Tm ratio, rather than absolute Tm^{3+} concentration, are depicted in Fig. 3b. Several observations can be made. Focusing on the optical fibers with Al_2O_3 content below 5 mol. %, there is no difference between the

Fig. 2. The representative decay curves of selected optical fibers, excitation wavelength in all cases $\lambda_{\text{exc.}} = 792 \text{ nm}$, a) P1338B, $^3\text{F}_4$ emission, b) P1338B, $^3\text{H}_4$ emission, c) P1618, $^3\text{F}_4$ emission, d) P1618, $^3\text{H}_4$ emission. Insets show decay times obtained from the 1/e value of intensity on the normalized decay curves.

Fig. 3. The fluorescence lifetime extrapolated to zero excitation power of the 3F_4 level, a) as a function of absolute Tm^{3+} concentration, b) Al/Tm or (Al+Y)/Tm ratio respectively. SD = solution doping, NP = nanoparticle doping, MC = molten-core method. Values in the parentheses give the Al_2O_3 content range.

solution and nanoparticle doping methods. Both techniques exhibit the same trend, which indicates that the Tm^{3+} ions are embedded in identical environments regardless of fabrication approach. Similar phenomenon was previously observed also in Ho^{3+} -doped fibers [14]. These results confirm that the Al_2O_3 nanoparticles are dissolved during the preform processing and fiber drawing around 2000 °C, and react with the silicon oxide to form a homogenous aluminosilicate matrix, identical as in the solution doped fibers. The reaction between Al_2O_3 nanoparticles and silica at high temperatures was also previously described in Ref. [46]. For low values of Al/Tm ratio below 10, which corresponds to approx. 5,000 ppm Tm^{3+} , the fluorescence lifetime drops below 400 μs due to concentration quenching. The maximum observed lifetime for these fibers is approx. 530 μs , achievable for Al/Tm ratio around 50, i.e. approx. 2,000 ppm Tm^{3+} . Further increasing the Al/Tm ratio brings no beneficial effect.

Moving on to fibers with increased Al_2O_3 contents above 5 mol. %, the fluorescence lifetime clearly increases even for identical values of the Al/Tm ratio. The highly-doped fibers prepared by nanoparticle doping possess relatively high lifetimes around 500 μs even at low Al/Tm ratios below 10, and reach up to 780 μs in fibers with low Tm^{3+} concentrations. This phenomenon can be attributed primarily to the reduction of multiphonon relaxation thanks to higher Al_2O_3 content. As previously stated, the Tm^{3+} ions in Al_2O_3 -rich glass become embedded in structural cavities formed by the Al^{3+} ions, which create a low-

phonon environment for the Tm^{3+} ions.

The beneficial effect of high alumina content may be further amplified by the phase separation of the glass matrix and creation of Al_2O_3 -enriched nanoparticles, as previously shown in Ref. [47]. The binary Al_2O_3 - SiO_2 system exhibits a metastable immiscibility in the solidus region, which leads to phase separation in fibers with Al_2O_3 content above approx. 5 mol. %, although the boundary is not precisely known. As previously shown, fibers with low Al_2O_3 content thus exhibit a homogenous matrix [48]. However, an increase of Al_2O_3 concentration causes phase separation and Al_2O_3 -enriched amorphous nanoparticles are created in the matrix, which represent a beneficial environment for Tm^{3+} ions. The creation of nanoparticles was confirmed in the P1618 fiber (approx. 9.5 mol. % of Al_2O_3), the TEM-EDS analysis is shown in Fig. 4. The EDS analysis confirmed the enrichment of the nanoparticles by Al_2O_3 , whereas the surrounding matrix was enriched by SiO_2 . The size of the nanoparticles below 20 nm ensures no negative effect on the background loss. The phase separation into Al_2O_3 -enriched nanoparticles was previously also observed in molten-core fibers [32], including the crystallization of various Al-based phases, such as crystalline Al_2O_3 [42].

The molten-core fibers with non-negligible content of Y_2O_3 follow a similar trend as the nanoparticle-doped fibers in Fig. 3b, with fluorescence lifetimes in close vicinity. Y_2O_3 in silica-rich glass serves a similar function as Al_2O_3 – it functions primarily as a trivalent network

Fig. 4. TEM-EDS analysis of P1618 fiber; TEM image and two representative spectra of Al-rich and Si-rich region.

modifier, which breaks the silica network and creates a beneficial, low-phonon environment for the Tm^{3+} ions [49,50]. The spectroscopic environment of Tm^{3+} ions thus appears similar in both types of fibers. However, the structural relationships in complex systems, such as $\text{Tm}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiO}_2$, represent a complex issue; more detailed research is necessary to clarify the structural role of Y_2O_3 in molten core fibers and the impact on the Tm^{3+} environment. Previous research suggests that the low concentrations of “inert” RE ions with no spectroscopic transition overlapping with investigated RE ion, such as Y^{3+} , La^{3+} , Yb^{3+} or Lu^{3+} , are beneficial for the fluorescence lifetime and laser operation, since the inert ions essentially “dilute” the clusters and reduce the rate of ET processes [26,51,52], but the structural and spectroscopic effects of Y_2O_3 in elevated contents remain to be properly understood.

The most significant benefit of the molten-core method lies in the possibility of achieving very high Al_2O_3 and Y_2O_3 concentrations while maintaining high (Al+Y)/Tm ratio around 40. As a result, the J481 fiber exhibits a very high value of lifetime, 710 μs , even for very high Tm^{3+} concentration around 16,700 ppm.

3.4. Fluorescence lifetime of the $^3\text{H}_4$ level (800 nm emission)

The fluorescence lifetimes of the investigated fibers measured for the resonantly-pumped emission from $^3\text{H}_4$ level (800 nm emission) are pictured in Fig. 5a as a function of absolute Tm^{3+} concentration. The observed trends are nearly identical to the $^3\text{F}_4$ lifetime. The fluorescence lifetime decreases with higher Tm^{3+} concentration due to concentration quenching, but increases with higher Al_2O_3 or Y_2O_3 content thanks to the reduction of multiphonon relaxation.

Interesting trends can be again observed when plotting the $^3\text{H}_4$ fluorescence lifetime as a function of Al/Tm ratio rather than absolute concentration, as depicted in Fig. 5b. The solution- and nanoparticle-doped fibers with low Al_2O_3 content below 5 mol. % exhibit identical trend as for the $^3\text{F}_4$ lifetime, with maximum value 30 μs reached for Al/Tm ratio around 50. Further increase of the Al/Tm ratio brings no beneficial effect.

Focusing on nanoparticle-doped or molten-core fibers with higher Al_2O_3 or Y_2O_3 content, the $^3\text{H}_4$ lifetime is enhanced for high values of Al/Tm ratio, i.e., the same effect as observed for the $^3\text{F}_4$ lifetime. However, the $^3\text{H}_4$ lifetime exhibits a strikingly different behavior when the Al/Tm ratio is decreased. While the $^3\text{F}_4$ lifetime of these highly-doped fibers remained enhanced in the entire range of Tm^{3+} concentrations and Al/Tm ratios, the $^3\text{H}_4$ lifetime bisects the trend for the solution-doped fibers at Al/Tm value around 40. As obvious from Fig. 5b, the highly-doped fibers with Al/Tm ratio below 20 exhibit very short $^3\text{H}_4$ lifetimes below 20 μs . The molten-core fibers exhibit a nearly identical trend, with the $^3\text{H}_4$ lifetime being significantly reduced for highly Tm^{3+} -doped fibers with (Al+Y)/Tm ratio around 40.

This phenomenon can be explained by the presence of the CR process, which depopulates the $^3\text{H}_4$ level and reduces its fluorescence

lifetime. In the highly-doped fibers prepared by nanoparticle doping or molten-core method, the rate of the CR process is higher than in the solution-doped fibers with lower Al_2O_3 and Tm^{3+} contents. The low values of the $^3\text{H}_4$ lifetime in highly-doped fibers with the Al/Tm ratios lower than 40 are a clear evidence of the efficient CR process. Considering the nanoparticle-doped fibers contain approx. 10 mol. % Al_2O_3 , the Al/Tm ratio around 40 corresponds to 5,000 ppm (approx. 1.5 wt%) of Tm^{3+} , which is in a good agreement with the generally given threshold for CR effect [2].

4. Discussion

In summary, a Tm^{3+} -doped fiber must meet several criteria in order to successfully operate in a 0.79 μm -pumped, 2 μm -emitting laser with efficiency higher than 40 % given by the Stokes limit. First, the fiber must contain a sufficiently high concentration of Tm^{3+} ions in order to trigger the CR process. As previously stated, concentrations of at least 5,000 ppm are necessary to overcome this limitation, but a truly sufficient laser operation (>60 %) is typically observed in fibers with at least 10,000 ppm [2]. Second, the fibers must contain homogeneously distributed, non-clustered Tm^{3+} ions in a low-phonon environment in order to ensure low rates of non-radiative processes, such as concentration quenching or multiphonon relaxation.

As established in the previous section, both of these criteria may be indicated by simultaneously, *i*) high value of $^3\text{F}_4$ fluorescence lifetime, showing low rates of concentration quenching and multiphonon relaxation, *ii*) low value of $^3\text{H}_4$ lifetime, indicating the depopulation of $^3\text{H}_4$ level by the CR process. Based on the evaluation of the spectroscopic properties in the previous sections, several fibers show a perspective for efficient laser operation, namely the nanoparticle-doped fibers P1545, P1598 and P1607, as well as the molten-core fibers, J458 and J481, all of which contain Tm^{3+} concentrations in excess of 10,000 ppm, high values of $^3\text{F}_4$ lifetime above 550 μs , and low values of $^3\text{H}_4$ lifetime below 30 μs .

The laser properties of the aforementioned nanoparticle-doped fibers were recently reported in Refs. [53,54], the achieved slope efficiencies were up to 55 % in the case of P1545 and P1598 fibers, and up to 65 % in the case of P1607 fiber. These results fall slightly short of literature and industry efforts, where slope efficiencies above 70 % are reported, see Ref. [2] and references therein. Further optimization of the fiber composition and geometry is necessary, e.g., increasing the Tm^{3+} content above 20,000 ppm while keeping the Al_2O_3 content above 8 mol. %, and the research is currently underway.

The nanoparticle doping method is attractive for the production of various specialty optical fibers with large mode area (LMA) and capable of achieving high powers owing to the reduction of non-linear effects. The nanoparticle doping was recently used for the fabrication of a pedestal-style large-core LMA fiber with very high $^3\text{F}_4$ lifetime above 650 μs [55]. The fiber was used for the construction of TDFA with slope

Fig. 5. The fluorescence lifetime extrapolated to zero excitation power of the $^3\text{H}_4$ level, a) as a function of absolute Tm^{3+} concentration, b) Al/Tm or (Al+Y)/Tm ratio respectively. SD = solution doping, NP = nanoparticle doping, MC = molten-core method.

efficiency as high as 61.8 % and up to 273 W output power, comparable with state-of-the-art TDFA devices. Furthermore, we recently demonstrated a proof-of-concept of a Tm^{3+} -doped nanostructured-core fiber with LMA. The fiber was prepared by the stack-and-draw method from nanoparticle-doped preform [56]. However, the slope efficiency achieved so far was fairly low, around 30 %, and further refinement of the preform composition, geometry and fabrication process is necessary.

The laser properties of the investigated molten-core fibers were recently demonstrated in Ref. [42], slope efficiencies up to 47 % were achieved so far. The relatively low increase of efficiency beyond the Stokes limit can be ascribed mainly to the high background losses, which are around 2 dB/m. Further refinement of the technological procedure is needed to obtain low-loss, highly efficient fibers. The molten-core fibers with high Al_2O_3 and Y_2O_3 contents remain promising for significant reductions of non-linear effects, such as stimulated Brillouin or Raman scattering, which are one of the main limiting factors for achieving high powers [31,33,34]. With regard to the high gain, achievable due to the high Al/Tm ratio even at high Tm^{3+} concentrations, potential areas of application include, e.g., short-cavity lasers.

5. Conclusion

We prepared a large set of thulium-doped silica fibers using three distinct methods – the traditional solution doping combined with MCVD, the more advanced nanoparticle doping and the molten-core method. The fluorescence lifetime of emission from $^3\text{F}_4$ and $^3\text{H}_4$ levels was measured in all fibers and evaluated with regard to composition and fabrication. The optical fibers with up to 5 mol. % of Al_2O_3 , prepared either by solution or nanoparticle doping, exhibit relatively low $^3\text{F}_4$ lifetimes, around 510 μs at maximum, due to the high rates of multiphonon relaxation in the silica-rich matrix. Increasing the Tm^{3+} content above 5,000 ppm causes the shortening of $^3\text{F}_4$ lifetime below 400 μs due to concentration quenching. No difference was observed between the solution and nanoparticle doping methods for optical fibers with Al_2O_3 content up to 5 mol. %, which indicates the Tm^{3+} environment is identical regardless of the method and starting compound, AlCl_3 solution or Al_2O_3 nanoparticle dispersion.

On the other hand, optical fibers with Al_2O_3 content above 5 mol. %, prepared either by nanoparticle doping or molten-core method, exhibited enhanced values of $^3\text{F}_4$ lifetime up to 780 μs thanks to the low phonon energy of alumino-silicate glass. Moreover, the phase separation of the glass matrix into Al_2O_3 -rich, amorphous nanoparticles embedding the Tm^{3+} ions was confirmed in fibers containing at least 9 mol. % of Al_2O_3 . This allowed the preparation of highly doped fibers with Tm^{3+} content above 10,000 ppm with long $^3\text{F}_4$ lifetime above 550 μs . In addition, the presence of efficient cross-relaxation effect was evidenced by the short values of $^3\text{H}_4$ lifetime below 20 μs in the highly-doped fibers.

The nanoparticle doping combined with MCVD and the molten-core method are promising methods for the fabrication of highly-doped optical fibers for applications in high-power, 0.8 μm -pumped lasers emitting around 2 μm . The advantage of nanoparticle doping lies in the low background loss below 0.1 dB/m, which allows highly-efficient laser operation, with up to 65 % slope efficiencies demonstrated so far. The molten-core fibers exhibit higher losses around 2 dB/m, which limits the efficiency; the main advantage of the method lies in the possibility of incorporating very high amounts of Al_2O_3 above 25 mol. %, which makes them prospective for short-cavity applications, the reduction of non-linear effects and potentially the generation of new laser wavelengths.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Petr Vařák: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Martin Leich:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Michal Kamrádek:** Writing – review & editing,

Investigation, Conceptualization. **Jan Aubrecht:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Ondřej Podrazký:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Ivo Bartoň:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Bára Švejkarová:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Alena Michalcová:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Katrin Wondraczek:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Matthias Jaeger:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Ivan Kašík:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation. **Pavel Peterka:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Pavel Honzátko:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data supporting the results of this study can be found in Ref. [57].

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